

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-GENERATED CONTENT FOR ENGLISH LESSONS: THEORY AND PRACTICAL INSIGHTS*Shumeiko N.**Researcher at Bratislava University of Economics and Business**ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7859-7519>***Abstract**

The Pearson Smart Lesson Generator (PSLG) is analyzed in this paper. A descriptive method is applied to examine the science behind how the PSLG can aid in preparing materials (e.g., tasks, learning games) for English lessons. The AI-generated lesson content encompasses a “lesson hook,” a glossary (a list of words, definitions, example sentences) and a vocabulary game, grammar (e.g., tasks to consolidate the knowledge about advanced comparatives and superlatives with prepositions), speaking, and reading (a text and questions for checking comprehension) tasks, and an “exit ticket.” The conclusion highlights the time-saving value of the PSLG.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, Pearson Smart Lesson Generator, English, reading, speaking, grammar.

Introduction

The rise in artificial intelligence-powered resources (platforms, applications, and tools that use artificial intelligence (AI) technology) has impacted university teaching and learning. There is no denying the benefits that AI has brought. However, there are growing concerns about the use of AI. Without any doubt, AI-generated materials are praised for saving time. However, AI-powered systems that generalize these materials are not always reliable. Despite limitations, AI can generate materials for teaching and learning English at universities. Creating activities, tasks, and materials for English classes is time-consuming. It is also an activity that requires creativity, which is not part of everyone’s skill set. AI-generated materials for English classes support teachers’ work. The ready-to-use content generated by the Pearson Smart Lesson Generator (PSLG) is appropriate for lessons thanks to the Pearson Global Scale of English (GSE) checks integrated into the PSLG.

AI brings opportunities to the educational sphere (UNESCO, 2025; UNESCO, 2024a; UNESCO, 2024b). Not long ago, we thoroughly explored online resources for promoting foreign language acquisition (Shumeiko & Krajčovičová, 2023; Shumeiko & Nypadymka, 2021; Spišiaková & Shumeiko, 2024, 2025). These days, we focus on AI (Shumeiko & Spišiaková, 2025; Shumeiko, 2024; Shumeiko & Osadcha, 2024). The feasibility of using AI in language education is analyzed by scholars in recently published papers. Researchers (Kushmar et al., 2022) focus on exploring the role of AI in the English language learning process. In their view, AI has the potential to transform the education system, empowering teachers with new opportunities and learners with new skills. AI resources allow teachers to support students’ learning needs with even greater attention. Scholars (Jimming & Ben Kei, 2024) hold the opinion that the use of AI chatbots contributes to enhancing English speaking skills. The challenges and affordances of utilizing AI in English language learning are analyzed scientifically (Crompton et al., 2024; Edmett et al., 2023; Shumeiko, 2024).

The *objective* of this paper is to explore the science behind the PSLG and present the AI-generated lesson’s content on the topic of company culture for teaching advanced learners of English at university.

Methods

The PSLG enables teachers to create lesson content. The PSLG is accessible through the Person English Portal (Smart Lesson Generator, 2025) and connected to the student’s book “Speak Out C1-C2” (Edwards et al., 2023). Creating supplemental teaching materials and activities for a lesson’s topic is a time-consuming task. The PSLG supports teacher’s work by creating additional AI-generated content that integrates seamlessly with the course.

The PSLG is characterized as an invaluable AI tool. This tool generates the lesson materials and assignments aligned with the Pearson Global Scale of English (GSE). The GSE is a scale (ranging from 10 to 90) for measuring English language proficiency (from A1 to C2). The topic of company culture is presented in this paper. The AI-powered resource PSLG created content and activities for this lesson topic designed for advanced English learners. This content (tasks and teaching materials) is appropriately leveled and automatically undergoes a quality control process by the GSE. The ready-to-use activities on the theme of company culture are offered for classwork, as additional materials, as assignments that complement coursebook content, or as activities that the teacher can further modify.

This paper proves the functionality and pedagogical value of the PSLG in preparing teaching materials for advanced English learners at universities. The potential of the PSLG is described. The principles of content selection and task format are verified. Then, AI-generated lesson materials (tasks, role-plays) by the PSLG are provided. A descriptive explanation of the PSLG’s capabilities and a critical analysis of teaching materials for learners at the C1-C2 level were conducted. The theoretical significance of this study lies in defining ways to utilize the PSLG. The practical significance lies in presenting tasks for conducting a lesson for advanced-level learners at the university.

The AI-generated activities by PSLG involve a three-step process: (1) Teachers select the type of activity. These activities include “lesson hooks,” a glossary, a grammar assignment, conversation starters, reading comprehension, and “exit tickets.” The PSLG uses the GSE learning objectives. In our paper, we pro-

vide AI-generated materials and activities for advanced-level (C1 to C2) learners of English, designed in accordance with the CEFR (note: the GSE is 73-85). (2) AI-generated content is filtered through several GSE filters, providing level-appropriate content. (3) Activities are delivered to the teacher in the PSLG tool and can be offered to students in class (Mayor, 2025).

Findings

In this article, we provide an example of the teaching materials created by the PSLG for the lesson topic "Company culture" (Edwards et al., 2023, p.40-41; Williams, 2023, p.79-81; Smart Lesson Generator, 2025). The PSLG generated the activities for this lesson. Selected materials are presented in this chapter of the article, such as the "lesson hook" (that gets advanced learners of English engaged with a compelling starter), a glossary (a list of words, definitions, example sentences, and a learning game), a communication starter, reading comprehension (a task that tests advanced learners of English reading comprehension with a text and multiple choice questions), an "exit ticket" (assess learners' understanding and reflect on a lesson).

An AI-generated "lesson hook"

At the beginning of the lesson (a "lesson hook"), every student is asked to imagine that he is a workplace culture consultant hired by two merging tech companies. The characteristics of the companies are as follows. One company is known for its liberal political views and casual atmosphere. The other company is on a sound financial footing but has strict traditional policies. The CEO is concerned that these differences might exacerbate divisions among employees. The teacher gives students 5 minutes to present their recommendations for creating a unified company culture. The question is arising: What key aspects would you focus on to ensure a smooth transition? (Smart Lesson Generator, 2025)

For the "lesson hook" stage of the lesson, the following AI-generated teacher notes are offered (Smart Lesson Generator, 2025): encourage learners to take notes on their groupmates' suggestions (practicing students' listening skills, enabling two-way communication); monitor language use; note down good examples of persuasive language, give feedback; collect various suggestions.

An AI-generated glossary

Understanding the meanings of words and phrases in company culture helps advanced learners of English improve their spoken fluency and memorize high-frequency collocations, as well as fixed and semi-fixed phrases, to recall them at the right moment in the workplace. An AI-generated vocabulary presentation on "Company culture" provides a list of words and expressions with definitions and example sentences (Appendix A).

A vocabulary presentation includes a game entitled "Policymaking Simulation" (Smart Lesson Generator, 2025). To run the game, the teacher divides the class into small groups of "policymakers." Each group receives a current social issue card (an example of a card: explain what a "toxic work culture" means, discuss whether you have experienced it, list signs of a toxic work culture, suggest how companies can manage

this issue, recommend possible ways forward). Using vocabulary words, groups must create and present a policy proposal (an example of a policy proposal: a toxic work culture includes poor communication and a lack of trust, all of which take a long time to trickle down into widespread dissatisfaction. Policy proposals include: using a secret ballot for employee feedback, utilizing exit polls to gather insights from employees to inform policy improvements, promoting respect, prioritizing education on unconscious bias, allocating resources to support services such as burnout prevention programs, and strengthening bonds across teams to encourage cross-departmental collaboration. Students must use at least six vocabulary words in their presentation. Other groups act as opposition parties and can challenge the proposals using the vocabulary. The teacher awards points for correct usage of language and creative problem-solving. This game helps advanced learners of English understand words and use them in practical contexts while engaging in critical thinking and public speaking.

While developing vocabulary, the following AI-generated teacher notes are offered (Smart Lesson Generator, 2025): create mini-discussions to incorporate words related to the lesson topic into conversation and use role-plays to practice using these words and expressions in professional contexts.

Grammar

The grammar section provides a definition, things to note, example sentences, and teacher notes (Smart Lesson Generator, 2025). At the C1 level, in a lesson focused on the theme of company culture, the ways to make comparisons using comparative and superlative forms combined with prepositions are explored. The grammar section includes rules and usage explanations of complex comparative structures (such as "significantly better than" and "far superior to"), prepositional phrases in comparisons (such as "as opposed to" and "in comparison with"), and idiomatic comparative expressions (such as "second to none" and "by far the most").

An AI-generated speaking task

Speaking fluency is a primary objective of learning a foreign language. Learners develop fluency when they are motivated to communicate. Engaging tasks are essential (Appendix B).

The time allocation for the communication starter is 20-25 minutes (5 minutes for individual ranking, 10 minutes for small group discussion, and 10 minutes for class discussion). Students work in groups of 3 to 4. The students are offered pre-teach key vocabulary (hybrid work model, mentoring, real-time feedback, work-life balance) (Smart Lesson Generator, 2025).

An AI-generated reading task

Learners who read regularly tend to have a more varied vocabulary. On the topic of "Company culture," the PSLG (Smart Lesson Generator, 2025) generated the text entitled "The Evaluation of Modern Workplace Culture: A Tech Industry Perspective." The text consists of 4 paragraphs. There are four questions for this text, along with suggested answers. The correct answers are shown with "✓" (Appendix C).

An AI-generated "exit ticket" task

In this part of the lesson, students are offered the opportunity to analyze how different leadership styles can influence employee behavior and organizational values. The question generated by the PSLG is designed to test and assess students' understanding of the concept of "company culture." This question is as follows: What aspects of today's lesson challenged your previous assumptions about workplace dynamics? Moreover, the teacher can offer an expansion task (Appendix D) for classwork or homework.

AI-generated teacher notes support the "exit ticket" part of the lesson. Particularly, it is recommended that students be encouraged to use specific business terms (e.g., exit polls, secret ballot) and share their views on the lesson topic.

Appendix A

An AI-generated* glossary on "Company culture"

Definitions:

- secret ballot: A method of voting in which voters mark their choices privately, ensuring anonymity and preventing coercion or intimidation; derived from the Italian 'ballotta' meaning a small ball used in voting
- take a long time to trickle down: A metaphorical phrase describing the gradual, often slow process by which benefits, changes, or effects eventually reach lower levels of a system or society from the top
- spread the word: To disseminate information or news through various channels, often through informal communication networks; an idiomatic expression emphasizing the active distribution of information
- prioritise: To arrange or address matters in order of their relative importance or urgency; from Latin 'prior' meaning earlier or first
- allocate resources: To distribute and assign available assets, funds, or materials in a strategic manner to achieve specific objectives or meet particular needs

Examples:

- secret ballot: The introduction of the secret ballot in the 19th century revolutionized democratic processes by enabling voters to express their true preferences without fear of repercussions.
- take a long time to trickle down: Although the new economic policies benefited major corporations immediately, it took a long time to trickle down to small businesses and individual workers.
- spread the word: Environmental activists utilized social media platforms to spread the word about the immediate need for climate action.
- prioritise: In times of crisis, healthcare administrators must prioritise the allocation of medical resources based on urgency and potential impact.
- allocate resources: The board of directors met quarterly to allocate resources among various departments, ensuring optimal utilization of the company's assets.

*a list of words, definitions, and example sentences are AI-generated by the PSLG
Source: *Smart Lesson Generator, 2025*

Conclusion

The PSLG supports teachers' work. This AI resource is a real time-saver. It can generate supplemental materials (tasks, learning games, texts, and questions) for English classes at the university. The ready-to-use activities, such as AI-generated lesson hooks, vocabulary presentations (including words, definitions, and sample sentences), and communication and reading tasks, can be further modified by the teacher for use in class or assigned as a home task.

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Appendix B**An AI-generated speaking task**

You are the HR Director of a multinational tech company planning to implement major workplace changes for the upcoming year. With a limited budget, you need to prioritize these initiatives based on their potential impact on employee satisfaction and company growth.

- Introduce a hybrid work model allowing employees to work remotely three days per week
- Establish a comprehensive leadership development program with executive mentoring and cross-functional rotation opportunities
- Implement an AI-powered performance management system with real-time feedback and personalized development plans
- Create an innovation lab with dedicated time for employees to work on passion projects and potential business solutions
- Launch a global wellness program including mental health support, fitness memberships, and work-life balance coaching

(a speaking task is AI-generated by the PSLG)

Source: *Smart Lesson Generator, 2025.*

Appendix C**An AI-generated reading task**

The Evolution of Modern Workplace Culture: A Tech Industry Perspective

In the rapidly evolving landscape of corporate culture, traditional workplace hierarchies, once as rigid as those of a hereditary monarch, are giving way to more fluid and dynamic structures. Silicon Valley's pioneering approach to organizational culture has fundamentally transformed how companies worldwide approach workplace dynamics. This shift, while revolutionary, has also served to exacerbate divisions between companies that embrace modern practices and those steadfastly clinging to conventional methodologies.

The digital era has introduced unprecedented challenges in maintaining professional boundaries. A careless social media post or an inappropriate email can jeopardise a person's chance of career advancement and leave a problematic digital footprint that may haunt them for years. However, the same technology that creates these risks also offers unprecedented opportunities for collaboration and innovation. Progressive companies are learning to harness these tools to strengthen bonds among remote teams while maintaining professional standards.

Rather than being a wet blanket on creativity, well-structured corporate cultures that warrant a second look are those that play to your particular strengths while fostering collective growth. Google's approach, for instance, demonstrates how shared values can drive innovation while maintaining employee satisfaction. Their policy of allowing employees to dedicate 20% of their time to personal projects has led to groundbreaking products while reinforcing their culture of innovation.

The implementation of inclusive workplace practices has become increasingly crucial as organizations cast a vote for diversity through their policies and actions. Progressive companies are taking decisive steps to eliminate discrimination, recognizing that diverse perspectives drive innovation and market understanding. Studies consistently demonstrate that companies embracing inclusive cultures outperform their competitors by significant margins, suggesting that cultural transformation isn't merely a social imperative but a business necessity.

1. What underlying transformation in contemporary business culture does the text primarily illustrate?

1. The shift from hierarchical frameworks toward adaptable organizational structures that prioritize innovation ✓
2. The implementation of mandatory technological solutions to enhance employee productivity levels
3. The standardization of management practices across different industrial sectors globally

2. How does the text characterize the relationship between technological advancement and professional conduct?

1. As a dual-edged phenomenon that presents both potential pitfalls and collaborative opportunities ✓
2. As a purely beneficial force that automatically enhances workplace communication
3. As a temporary trend that will eventually be replaced by traditional business practices

(the text and questions are AI-generated by the PSLG)

Source: Smart Lesson Generator, 2025.

Appendix D

An AI-generated “exit ticket” task

Expansion task

Imagine you are a cultural transformation consultant hired by a traditional company that needs to adapt to remote work while maintaining its strong collaborative culture. Design a detailed three-point strategy that addresses both the challenges and opportunities of this transition. Consider aspects such as virtual team building, maintaining company values, and fostering innovation in a digital environment.

(the task is AI-generated by the PSLG)

Source: Smart Lesson Generator, 2025.

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